

SEISMEC

Supporting European Industry Success Maximization
through Empowerment Centred development

D3.1

Pilot Implementation and Monitoring Plan

Technische Universität Berlin

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Abstract

The Pilot Implementation and Monitoring Plan report provides a comprehensive and detailed outline for all pilot activities. This document will reflect project developments, ensuring systematic and efficient implementation. The report includes the detailed plans for monitoring pilot progress, research methodologies, key performance indicators (KPIs), protocols and framework to achieve the projects' objectives. Additionally, it encompasses ethics and privacy in data management to ensure safety and security throughout the project. The report aims to facilitate timely and accurate progress reporting, ensuring the pilot activities are conducted effectively, and contributing to the project's success. Ultimately, the Pilot Implementation and Monitoring Plan serves as a crucial framework, guiding the execution of SEISMEC's pilot activities to achieve the project's goals. Further developments will occur during piloting process which will be reflected in Monitoring Document of D7.3 and D7.4

Keywords

Pilot, plans, assessments, objectives, ethics, data management

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Executive summary	8
1 Introduction.....	9
1.1.1 Piloting Objectives and Scopes.....	10
1.1.2 Piloting Methodology and Limitation.....	12
2 Overview	13
2.1 Summary of SEISMEC Pilots.....	13
2.1.1 Description of Pilots.....	13
2.1.2 SEISMEC Advanced Technology Overview	23
2.1.3 SEISMEC Shift: CAPS factors and Innovation Areas.....	25
2.1.4 KPIs Criteria for Evaluation.....	31
2.1.5 Challenges in Human-centric Research	35
2.2 Piloting Process Methodology	36
2.2.1 Piloting Planning Activities Conducted.....	38
2.2.2 Pilots' Focus Area of Improvement.....	43
2.2.3 Pilots' Tasks of Innovation	44
2.2.4 Pilots' CAPS factors.....	47
3 Case Study Research and Method.....	49
3.1 Preparation Phase.....	53
3.2 Action Research.....	55
3.3 Evaluation Phase	57
4 Protocols, Frameworks, and Challenges.....	60
4.1 Data collection protocols of WP1 & WP2	60
4.2 Application Framework for WP4 & WP5	61
5 Piloting Schedule	61
6 Ethics, Privacy and Data Management.....	63
6.1 Data Management.....	63
6.2 Data Privacy Related/ Required Agreements	63
6.3 Ethics compliance: three-level approach.....	65
7 Conclusion.....	66
8 References.....	67

List of figures

Figure 1. European Industrial Strategy	11
Figure 2. SEISMEC Pilot Structure	11
Figure 3. SEISMEC Partners and pilots -indication, subject to change (Source: DoA, 2024).....	22
Figure 4. Quadrant of potential methods and tools (Rohrer, 2022).....	38
Figure 5. Three phases on case study research proces.....	51
Figure 6. Preparation phase elements	54
Figure 7. Empathy map on user persona (Gray, 2017 with adjustment)	55
Figure 8. Action research phase elements	57
Figure 9. Technology radar following CAPS factors (Smith, 2018 with adjustment)	57
Figure 10. Evaluation phase elements	59

List of tables

Table 1. Relationship between research activities and project’s objectives	12
Table 2. Changes in pilot partnership between DoA and GA.....	21
Table 3. Key questions of benchmarking exercises on CAPS factors	29
Table 4. Pilots intended and current TRL from reference studies	31
Table 5. KPIs on Worker Feedback	33
Table 6. KPIs on CAPS factors based on benchmarking exercise	34
Table 7. Initial Pilot Workshop in M4-M6	39
Table 8. Pilot Workshop Encryption.....	42
Table 9. Pilot advanced technology and area of improvements.....	45
Table 10. Pilots’ Tasks of Innovation.....	46
Table 11. Pilot CAPS factor.....	48
Table 12. Template of Pilot Research Plan based on Innovation Tasks	52
Table 13. Piloting Schedule based on recent updates	62

Acronyms and definitions

CAPS	Creativity & Collaboration; Autonomy & Automation; Productivity & Privacy; Safety & job Satisfaction
DoA	Description of Action
EEA	European Economic Area
FGD	Focus Group Discussions
GA	General Assembly
KPI	Key Performance Index
M	Month
MS	Milestone
SRL	System Readiness Level
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
WP	Work Package

Executive summary

The SEISMEC project aims to demonstrate an empowered, human-centred, and ethical development of digital and industrial sectors across various industries in Europe. The piloting process, a continuous and iterative procedure, requires regular updates and immediate attention when changes occur. Pilots will be involved in four tasks of innovation areas that require contextual strategies to achieve desired technological advancements. Each pilot may address different spectrums and focuses with tailored strategies derived from the four tasks of innovation areas.

Within their distinctive elements, the piloting process must be closely monitored and coordinated to ensure progress and address issues promptly. The methodology involves direct contact with pilots, organize workshops, and monitor the cross-communication among different partners to ensure alignment and progress. To facilitate effective collaboration and ensure the project's success, it is recommended to establish a clear communication loop among all partners, including pilots, institutions, researchers, engineers, and designers. Closely monitoring and coordinating the piloting process requires regularly updated reports on essential changes. As such, this document presents the current framework for piloting activities, which further updates will be delivered in Monitoring Documents D7.3 and D7.4.

1 Introduction

Globally, the Industry is undergoing a momentous shift that has reshaped the expectation of productivity and efficiency in workplace practices. Technology advancements in Industry 4.0, such as ubiquitous computing and artificial intelligence have become at the forefront of flexible and data-driven decision-making for improving productivity in industries (Adel, 2022). However, in 2021, only eight percent of European enterprises were documented adopting the technologies (Meyers and Springford, 2023). With unpredictable circumstances happening in the past 5 years, including the pandemic and digital acceleration, as well as the EU's ageing population, it is necessary to create a flexible and cooperative environment to achieve goals in industry, making the technology become significantly crucial. By adopting human-centric approaches, the revolution of Industry 5.0 focuses on a two-way relationship between empowered human practices and new technologies, improving the contextuality of efficiency in industrial production.

SEISMEC will demonstrate an empowered, human-centred and ethical development of digital and industrial sectors across different industries in Europe. Through human-centric approaches, SEISMEC aims to increase inclusiveness which is measured in CAPS factors: Creativity, Collaboration, Autonomy, Automation, Productivity, Privacy, Safety and job Satisfaction. The factors are incorporated within a two-way engagement shown in feedback and co-development ideas from users as well as plans and innovations from companies to achieve an empowered human-centric Industry 5.0. Furthermore, human-centricity are also measured in the four different innovation areas in order to bring the advanced technologies beyond their state-of-art.

Therefore, this report aims to document the research implementation process of SEISMEC pilots and partners throughout the project. To achieve that, we outline the objectives and scopes as well as limitation of the piloting activity in this chapter. Further, the document is structured into a Piloting Process Overview, a

Summary of Research Methods and Tools, a Data Collection Protocol and Frameworks, a Piloting Schedule, and an Ethics, Privacy and Data Management.

1.1.1 Piloting Objectives and Scopes

The background of SEISMEC is described in two-folds. First, the advanced technologies have enabled continuous tracking and monitoring, making the workers and workspaces more visible and accessible to managerial oversight. Second, the need of flexible and supportive environment has increased the desire of fulfilment in work environment. These points demonstrate a critical need in shift from 4.0 perspectives towards Industry 5.0, which focuses on the relationship between empowering human practices and new technologies. SEISMEC will demonstrate the concept of human-centrism across a diverse set of 14 industrial ecosystem in the European Industrial Strategy (See **Figure 1**), with the objectives are:

- **Showing** how human solutions empower a skilled, value-driven and creative industry workforce;
- **Understanding and resolving** sociotechnical, financial, regulatory and ethical tensions of workers and work organisations associated with advanced digital technologies;
- **Defining and testing procedures and tools** for the design, implementation and redevelopment of advanced technologies;
- **Formulating evidence-based recommendations** tailored to relevant stakeholders through innovation practices which connect workers, industrial actors, policy makers and relevant EU research and innovation initiatives.

Figure 1. European Industrial Strategy

SEISMEC will focus on pilot implementation, which will be done iteratively throughout the majority of project’s timeframe. Within a diverse set of partners and sectors involved, SEISMEC will apply transversal research to provide good data collection throughout piloting activity. **Figure 2** shows the flow of piloting structures and methodologies in relation to work packages (shown by numbers in circles), outlining a transversal analysis intersection of project design stages and operational environment of the pilot.

Figure 2. SEISMEC Pilot Structure

To achieve project objectives, SEISMEC consists of nine research activities:

Main activities	SEISMEC Objectives			
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)
1. Theoretical underpinning of human-centric approach to technology and organisation and translation into human-centric interventions (WP1)	X	X	X	
2. CAPS assessments of 17 pilot employee situations according (WP3)	X	X		X
3. CAPS assessments of 17 pilot company performance situations (WP3)	X	X		X
4. Cross-case assessments of 17 pilot of technology impact (WP4)	X	X		
5. Develop macro-understanding of impacts human-centric approaches in 17 pilots (WP5)	X	X		
6. Develop human-centric support tools for advanced technology contexts (WP2)		X	X	
7. Conduct innovation camps for all major stakeholder groups (WP6)				X
8. Conduct regulation analysis (AI-act; standard formulation) (WP5)		X		X
9. Testing human-centric interventions (WP3)			X	

Table 1. Relationship between research activities and project's objectives

1.1.2 Piloting Methodology and Limitation

In the piloting activity, we aim to identify and to investigate the scopes of piloting activities through the main research questions as follows:

- How do human-centric approaches, measured by CAPS factors, impact the inclusiveness, productivity and competitiveness of pilots? And how do these approaches facilitate the pilots in achieving empowered and human-centred advanced technologies within different innovation areas?
- What strategies and methodologies are taken in monitoring and coordinating the piloting process to ensure progress and issue resolution?

Furthermore, it is important to acknowledge the limitation that the piloting activity is an iterative process continuously conducted throughout the project. As such, this document is not yet finalised. At this stage, we have developed and tested the framework for piloting activities; however, further details and updates will be required as the project progresses. These updates will be documented annually and continuously incorporated in Monitoring Documents D7.3 and D7.4.

2 Overview

2.1 Summary of SEISMEC Pilots

This section presents the summary of pilots in SEISMEC project as follows: first, we provide a brief description of pilot partners and their representatives. Second, we outline the objectives and scopes of piloting activity. Next, the document discusses SEISMEC Shift, highlighting the CAPS factors (Creativity, Collaboration, Autonomy, Automation, Productivity, Privacy, Safety, and Job Satisfaction) and the innovation areas each pilot focuses on. Then, the KPIs criteria are used for evaluation to measure the success and impact of the piloting activities. Finally, it presents the challenges in human-centric research, which include iterative processes as limitation for this document.

Next sections will briefly describe the pilot partners, the advanced technologies in SEISMEC, CAPS factors and innovation areas of SEISMEC Shift, KPIs criteria for evaluation in SEISMEC, and potential challenges in human-centric research.

2.1.1 Description of Pilots

SEISMEC investigates 17 pilots from 14 industries across European countries from various sectors and with different company sizes. A diverse set of pilots is required to illustrate the feasibility of human-centric industry in a wide range of contexts. The industries involved in SEISMEC include aerospace, agri-food, construction, culture and creative, digital, semiconductor, energy, healthcare, transport, mobility, security, textile, tourism and human resources which are spread across Croatia, Lithuania, Poland, Serbia, Romania, Austria, Belgium,

Turkey, France, Netherlands, Germany, Italy, Slovenia, and Portugal. The list of pilot partnership is presented in **Table 2**. **Table 3** shows the pilots' country of origin, and their representatives and **Figure 3** displays the composition of the partners' country of origin in the European landscape. The following section outlines the description of pilot partners in SEISMEC.

1. Zagreb Airport, Croatia (ZAG)

Legal name: Medunarodna zračna luka Zagreb DD

FOD inspection at airports involves detecting potential safety hazards by objects in operational areas. Currently, inspectors perform this task by walking or driving around with the naked eye at least four times a day. To enhance safety, reliability, and inclusivity, SEISMEC will co-develop and implement an AI-driven, real-time, and mobile inspection system mounted on a car and connected to a mobile data processing and interface system. It also changes the functions of inspectors, who now can perform inspections through advanced technologies. More workers can be included to carry out inspections (e.g., including people with reduced mobility). Additionally, advanced technology co-developed in SEISMEC will also enable creation of FOD database for all FOD detected in different operational or maneuvering areas at the airport. Collected and stored data will allow further detailed analysis to safety and operational managers, which will benefit in the improvement of operational & safety procedures, and at the end will simplify and improve the process for the inspectors and increase the level of safety.

2. Kvaletitas, Lithuania (Kvaletitas)

Legal name: Uzdaroji Akcine Bendrove Kvaletitas

Kvaletitas is a functional food company with 6 employees and 100+ products, each with a specific technological configuration and logistic needs. SEISMEC will implement AI and IoT technologies to support workers in decision making for this complex range of products, using explainable AI to enhance capabilities. This will bring the tasks and functions of workers to a higher level, monitoring and configuration of food processes. As a result, Kvaletitas can innovate its business model by expanding the range and increasing the value of its products.

3. MC, MCH, Portugal (MC, MCH)

Legal name: MC Shared Services S.A, Modelo Continente Hipermercados S.A. In the logistics operations of Modelo Continente Hipermercados (MCH), there is a warehouse designated as a test bed for various technological advances designed to increase efficiency, effectiveness, and the well-being of workers. The aim of this project is to investigate and implement various technologies to automate processes and tasks in the warehouse operations of a retail industry. With SEISMEC, MCH will analyse the impact in terms of efficiency of operations, the associated costs and the well-being, safety and satisfaction of workers in relation to the collaborative use of technology to assist operators in tasks such as the manual handling of loads, the transportation of goods within the warehouse, as well as in the support areas of warehouse maintenance. Thus, improving general working conditions and reducing repetitive tasks.

4. Mostostal Warsaw, Poland (MOW)

Legal name: Mostostal Warszawa SA

Mostostal is a construction company based in Poland that specialises in the design, construction, and modernization of various infrastructure projects. SEISMEC will coimplement with solutions that include AI technology for detecting risky situations using machine learning and identify preliminary assumption for construction projects. SEISMEC will draw upon its experience in Digital Twins and their potential to enhance the construction process. Moreover, the company will leverage its involvement in the BUILDSPACE and ASSISTIoT projects, where it has acquired knowledge and expertise in localising and detecting risky situations. This will reconfigure transparent and explainable technology that empowers workers through data access, personalisation, and ownership.

5. NS Web Development, Serbia (NS Web)

Legal name: NS Web Development Doo Novi Sad

NS Web Development makes 2D/3D non-violent and educational games and cartoons. Employee satisfaction, inclusion and well-being is crucial in

producing high-quality content. However, communication tools, time and resources can be limiting factors. To overcome these challenges, SEISMEC will co-implement Generative AI technology. This can improve worker capacity, enhance communication, and create a more efficient and effective job environment. These measures foster creativity, facilitate collaboration, and increase job satisfaction.

6. NTT Data, Romania (NTTD)

Legal name: NTT Data Romania SA

NTT DATA is a global information technology company that offers IT Solutions to businesses and governments. The People Experience Redesign (PRD) initiative aims to improve the work environment for NTT Data. Both physically and broadly, to enhance job satisfaction and employee retention. One of the key challenges faced in the post-pandemic context was the lack of interaction and learning opportunities within teams. SEISMEC plans to leverage PRD concepts to develop a new interactive employee journey. This approach can help identify crucial moments in the employee journey and create personalised experiences based on design thinking methodology, aligned with individual values and needs.

7. Infineon, Austria (IFAT)

Legal name: Infineon Technologies Austria AG

Infineon is a world-leading company in semiconductor solutions. The company is experimenting with the introduction of AI and data analysis technologies in its in-work learning and skills development process. Infineon will integrate SEISMEC's explainability and privacy-preserving monitoring solutions in this process to enhance technology acceptance and worker empowerment. These methods represent an innovative way to improve the skills of workers through their interaction with AI-based technologies and introduce human-centric engagement for AI solutions.

8. ATLAS Copco, Belgium (ATLAS Copco)

Legal name: Atlas Copco Airpower NV

Atlas Copco is a multinational industrial company that provides various products and services to customers in multiple industries worldwide. Atlas Copco aims to enhance AI in HR tasks, address technician shortages, improve employee satisfaction, and reduce worker turnover. The three-year HR strategy emphasises human-centered solutions, gender diversity, and a more appealing work environment. Key discussions focused on technology adoption challenges, productivity, and employee retention strategies. SEISMEC will collaborate on integrating an AI-based solution for service engineers and technical support. The application of this technology will be reconfigured to enhance inclusivity and promote reskilling opportunities.

9. ATES Windpower, Turkey (ATES)

Legal name: Ates Celik Insaat Taahhut Proje Muhendislik Sanayi Vi Ticaret Anonim Sirketi

ATES Windpower is a company in wind energy. The physical training such as 'safety', 'welding' and 'working at height' during new welder recruitment can pose a significant risk to their safety and confidence. To mitigate the risk, SEISMEC will co-implement AR-VR-XR technologies, creating an immersive and less stressful learning environment. Trainees get a realistic understanding of the welding process while reducing psychological stress. This will enable workers to complete their training more effectively and safely.

10. WZC De Dijleland, Belgium (DIJ)

Legal name: Woonzorgnet-Dijleland

The Residential Care Centre Dijleland has a care facility in Leuven for elderly people with dementia, called De Wingerd (CCC). The CCC has developed a new care concept in which "human-centric working" should be integrated into "cooperative centric care". The 'cooperative centric care' concept involves all kinds of external groups (informal carers, students, residents, neighbours, volunteers) based on their competencies and capabilities in providing all kinds of different forms of care. The prerequisite for this concept to work is that technology becomes 'cooperative centric'. The CCC wants to upgrade the existing, but insufficiently connected, technologies it has in use with AI

technology. The aim is to use that innovative technology to connect the needs of the residents to the way care planning is done in the organisation.

11. Michelin, France (Michelin)

Legal name: Manufacture Francaise Des Pneumatiques Michelin

Michelin produces and sells automotive tires. SEISMEC will co-develop a task recommender application to support workers in various environments. This AI application enables real-time task scheduling on complex industrial equipment aids workers in anticipating upcoming tasks. Operators will have decision-making tools for automated equipment, ensuring worker engagement and skilling based on information from these workers.

12. THALES, France (THALES)

Legal name: Thales Six GTS Frans SAS

Thales is a French multinational company that provides advanced technologies and solutions to protect citizens, critical infrastructure and sensitive data. SEISMEC will co-implement a control interface for drones and VR headsets. This interface would enable users to manipulate the drone via the headset. The pilot can be configured for multiple scenarios, such as search and rescue, and first responders. This would enhance creativity in finding viable solutions for search and rescue scenarios, as well as the upskilling quality of workers.

13. SELANA, Netherland

Legal name: Go Tulip BV

SELANA is a manufacturer of light electric vehicles. SEISMEC will test new technologies to enhance worker satisfaction and upskilling at different stages of the product cycle. The pilot will focus on understanding and exploring Human in the Loop Automation (HITL) for inventory & stock management; assessing and implementing generative AI for industrial design where individual skill-sets are seamlessly integrated, fostering collaboration between human creativity and technological advancement to drive innovation; improving health & safety in the warehouse by leveraging new

technologies to create a safer and more conducive working environment while training and upskilling workers.

14. Farm Now, Germany (FARM.NOW)

Legal name: Farmnow Shared Vertical Impact Farming GmbH

FarmNow works on redesigning central urban areas to create tech and infrastructure for vertical farming enabling mutual learning, kind of like an "Air BnB" of vertical farm space so people can grow micro-farms in small private areas like balconies and terraces in the neighbourhood. SEISMEC will co-develop and co-implement training for workers on new skills and knowledge to become urban farming technicians involving dashboard analysis, plant care, system maintenance, data analysis and logistics. Biometrics of workers and plants would be tested to ensure comfortable working conditions for workers ensuring worker satisfaction.

15. Fratelli Piacenza, Italy (PIAC)

Legal name: Fratelli Piacenza S.P.A

Fratelli Piacenza produces high-quality textiles and fabrics. SEISMEC will co-implement AI techniques through a microservice-based deployment architecture, either as a cloud service or on-site. A knowledge base supported by a testbed environment will guide users to AI techniques and fine-tune parameters for defect detection. Human operators will have real-time interaction through augmented reality, voice assistance, and mobile-based human-computer interaction methods. This will enable employee co-design of technology tied to reward mechanisms, as well as lower strain for quality controllers.

16. Arctur, Slovenia (Arctur)

Legal name: Arctur Racunalniski Inzeniring Doo

Arctur (50 employees) is an innovation specialist company working to inspire and empower organisations to reinvent themselves and co-create products and services, contributing to a more sustainable and equitable future for the European tourism sector. In 2021 Arctur has become the Ambassadors of the Slovenian economy because of its Tourism 4.0 achievements. SEISMEC will

co-develop demand estimation methods that allow for better work allocation between tourism providers, collaboration between providers in the region for joint business advantages and skilling to enable workers to take advantage of these resources.

17. Malt, European (MALT)

Legal name: Malt Community

Malt is a European online job platform that connects freelance professionals with businesses seeking their services. Analysing existing collected data, such as click-through-rate and reviews, SEISMEC will co-develop a model whereby machine learning will be used to analyse data such as click-through rates and reviews, in order (1) identify existing biases and (2) implement a system to mitigate them. This machine learning will create inclusive online marketplaces where success is not limited by one's background, age, gender, or location. The implementation of AI-powered recruitment can serve as a means to promote inclusivity and mitigate human-led biases in the hiring process

Description of Action (01.01.2024)		General Assembly Amendment (24.05.2024)		
Name of Partner	Ecosystem	Name of Partner	Ecosystem	Location
ZAG	Aerospace	ZAG	Aerospace	Croatia
Kvalitetas	Agrifood	Kvalitetas	Agrifood	Lithuania
ARIVIA	Agrifood	MC,MCH	Agrifood	Portugal
MOW	Construction	MOW	Construction	Poland
NSWD	Creative	NSWD	Creative	Serbia
NTTD	Digital	NTTD	Digital	Romania
IFAT	Electronics	IFAT	Electronics	Austria
ATLAS Copco	Energy intensive	ATLAS Copco	Energy intensive	Belgium
ATES	Energy renewable	ATES	Energy renewable	Türkiye
Healthcare Pilot	Health	Djileland	Health	Belgium
MICHELIN	Automotive	MICHELIN	Automotive	France
THALES	Civil security	THALES	Civil security	France
SELANA	Proximity	SELANA	Proximity	Netherlands
FarmNow	Retail & Agrifood	FarmNow	Retail & Agrifood	Germany
PIAC	Textile	PIAC	Textile	Italy
ARCTUR	Tourism	ARCTUR	Tourism	Slovenia
Malt	Cross-sector	Malt	Cross-sector	Multiple

Table 2. Changes in pilot partnership between DoA and GA

Figure 3. SEISMEC Partners and pilots -indication, subject to change (Source: DoA, 2024)

2.1.2 SEISMEC Advanced Technology Overview

SEISMEC pilots will apply variety of advanced technologies such as artificial intelligent (AI) and other ubiquitous computing technologies which are implemented to reach the goal of Industry 5.0 using human-centred approaches. Pilots may present one or more advanced technologies based on necessity and long-term goals. SEISMEC pilots will apply a set of technologies that are considered state-of-the-art for promoting human-centrism in industrial environment (Longo et al., 2020) as follows:

AI (Artificial Intelligence): Artificial Intelligence refers to a technology that enables human intelligence simulation and complex skills in machines (Sheikh et al., 2023).

AT (Activity and Motion Trackers): Activity and Motion Trackers are devices or applications that monitor and record physical metrics and movement activity (Shin et al., 2019).

AR (Augmented Reality): Augmented Reality is a combination of technologies that overlays digital information, such as images, sounds, or other data, onto the real-world environment in real time, enhancing the user's perception of reality (Mekni & Lemieux, 2014).

BD (Big Data): Big Data refers to extremely large datasets and information assets with high volume, velocity and variety, which require specific technology and analytical methods for its transformation into value (De Mauro et al., 2015).

CC (Cloud Computing): Cloud Computing is a model for enabling ubiquitous on-demand network access to a shared pool of configurable computing resources over the internet, including data storage, servers, databases, networking, and software. It allows a rapid provision and release with minimal management effort or service provider interaction (Mell & Grance, 2011)

DA (Digital Voice-enabled Assistants): Digital Voice-enabled Assistants are AI-powered systems that respond to voice commands and enable the devices to perform tasks remotely from the users (Hoy, 2018).

HMD (Health Monitoring Devices): Health Monitoring Devices are electronic devices that can measure and track health-related metrics as well as monitor how the users carry their daily activities (Mshali et al., 2018).

HMI (Human Machine Interface): Human Machine Interface refers to a system that allows an operator to view and control machinery, allowing supervisory control and interaction between user and the machine (Malviya et al., 2024).

IoT (Internet of Things): The Internet of Things is a network of physical objects being connected to the internet enabling them to see, hear, and perform in exchanging information and coordinate with other devices (Al-Fuhaqa, 2015).

MD (Mobile Devices): Mobile Devices are portable computing devices such as smartphones, tablets, and wearable gadgets that allow users to access information, communicate, and perform a wide range of functions on the go (Huq et al., 2015).

SIM (Simulation): Simulation is the imitation of the operation of a real-world process or system over time. It involves creating a model that represents the system being studied, and it is used in various fields such as training, research, and entertainment (Law, 2015).

SN (Social Network): Social Networks are platforms that facilitate the creation and sharing of information, ideas, interests, and other expression through virtual communities and networks which also enable collaborative working and smart interaction (Boyd and Ellison, 2007; Kaplan and Haenlein, 2010).

TOS (Teleoperated Systems): Teleoperated Systems are systems operated remotely by humans. These systems can perform tasks in environments that are hazardous, inaccessible, or require precise control, such as robotic surgery or remote-controlled drones (Niemeyer et al., 2008).

VR (Virtual Reality): Virtual Reality is a technology that immerses users in a completely virtual environment of visual, auditory and tactile senses in which users can interact within the environment, giving them a more realistic experience (Wu, 2024).

WD (Wearable Devices): Wearable Devices are electronic technologies or computers that are incorporated into items of clothing and accessories, which can perform various functions such as monitoring or providing notifications (Muench et al., 2017; Wright and Keith, 2014).

WES (Work Environment Sensors): Work Environment Sensors are devices used to monitor various aspects of the workplace environment, such as temperature, humidity, light, noise levels, and air quality. These sensors help in maintaining optimal working conditions and ensuring safety (Bardhan et al., 2013; Yang et al., 2018).

A table of technologies per pilot will be provided after the start-up of all pilots.

2.1.3 SEISMEC Shift: CAPS factors and Innovation Areas.

Following section describes the SEISMEC shift on CAPS factors and innovation areas which are crucial to understand the human-centrism context of SEISMEC in order to conduct transversal analysis in piloting activity. The CAPS factors and the four innovation areas are crucial components linked to Key Performance Indexes (KPIs) for evaluation criteria which will further be explained in the next Chapter 2.1.4.

SEISMEC CAPS Factors

The revolution of Industry 5.0 is a collaborative effort between humans and machines to improve production efficiency (Adel, 2022). Instead of widening digital gaps and replacing humans due to technological advancement, Industry 5.0 aims to leverage advanced technologies to help users work more efficiently. SEISMEC demonstrates the application of technological advancement, which aims to simultaneously empower the workforce and enhance industrial competitiveness through the **SEISMEC Shift**. The SEISMEC Shift focuses on four key empowerment factors referred as **CAPS**:

- Collaboration and Creativity,
- Autonomy and Automation,
- Privacy and Productivity,
- Safety and job Satisfaction

CAPS is the framework of analysis from SEISMEC and aims to transcend the tensions between human empowerment and economic competitiveness. CAPS presents four key empowerment factors which combine employee's empowerment with fair and ethical digital practices in order to enhance industrial competitiveness. CAPS factors will focus on human factors and be used as an assessment of the pilots' guidelines and state of art in human-centrism approaches. **WPI Framework for Human-Centric Assessment** describes the CAPS factors as follows:

Collaboration: Involves mutual goal understanding, pre-emptive task co-management and shared progress tracking (Wang et al., 2020)

Creativity: Ability to produce work that is both novel (i.e., original) and appropriate (i.e., useful) (Sternberg & Lubart, 2014)

Autonomy: Capacity of an individual, agent, or system to make decisions and govern themselves independently with minimal or no external assistance (Estevez Almenzar et al., 2022)

Automation: Use of systems and technologies to perform previously human tasks with minimal or without external intervention, using mechanical devices to automate the production (Gupta & Arora, 2011).

Privacy: Sharing information only within socially agreed contextual boundaries (Finn et al., 2013).

Productivity: The relation of output (i.e., produced goods) to input (i.e., consumed resources) for a specific production situation (Tangen, 2002a; Singh et al., 2000; Rogers, 1998).

The CAPS factors are used to determine the key questions within three categories or levels of employees, organisations, and industries as described in detail in the document **Deliverable 1.1 Benchmarking of concepts and dimensions of human-centrism**. The questions will be used as practical tools to discover and to instrumentalize the concept of human-centrism. The answers to the questions aim to assess the pilots' orientation towards the benchmarking of human-centric advanced technology applications. presents the key questions and examples of Likert scale in regard to CAPS factors used to measure the human-centrism of the advanced technologies (**Table 4**). The detailed exercises of benchmarking human-centrism are explained further in the Deliverable 1.1.

	Employees	Organisation	Industries	Likert scale exercises
Collaboration	How do employees perceive new technology? How have they been involved in the development and new technology implementation?	How has the organisational culture prioritised collaboration in the implementation of advanced technologies (e.g., integrating AI in daily work practices)?	How has effective collaboration been promoted and sustained within the broader industry and in relation to stakeholders?	The degree of collaboration between humans and digital systems (robots, machines, digital tools) within your organization.
Creativity	How do employees experience and seen as valued for their innovative ideas in their daily work?	What strategies have been employed to ensure that employee creativity is effectively integrated with new technology tools in collaborative projects?	How enhanced creativity improved efficiency and innovation in your industry?	Organizational results, performance, efficiency and productivity are influenced by the relation between human - centricism / affect and creativity.
Autonomy	How do employees experience their own autonomy and decision-making potentials with organizational boundaries?	What changes to organisational structures or processes have or will be made to support greater employee autonomy?	How open and supportive is the broader industrial sector towards employee autonomy? How does this affect decision-making processes within the supply chain?	The degree of human autonomy based on human - machine interaction.
Automation	What are the feedbacks and process mechanisms for the integration of	How would you describe your organisation’s approach to integrating	In what ways does automation serve to improve the industrial	Human safety, trust, workload and behaviour are taken into

	automation in daily employee tasks?	automation into your work processes?	sector and how does this contribute to the overall wellbeing of workers?	consideration in automating tasks and activities within your organization.
Privacy	How aware are employees about how their data is being used for organisational purposes?	How does your organisation integrate privacy-enhancing policies into its operations to support employees and their data?	What human-centric initiatives are in place to address privacy concerns on an industry-wide level?	Occupational risks are taken into consideration in human-centric computing, human-machine interaction and collaboration and integration of AI in human work processes.
Productivity	How do employees experience expectations of productivity while having flexible working arrangements?	How does the organisation ensure that advanced technologies intended to optimise productivity are ethically grounded and accountable?	How do productivity expectations align with human-centric objectives of the organisation?	Data-driven approaches are implemented to enhance productivity and privacy.
Safety	How has employee safety (and security) become a crucial component of work routines? How have employees participated in identifying and	How is human-centricity prioritised in your approach to safety measures (e.g., risk management, AI safety, training and support mechanisms)?	How have standards for safety been developed across the industrial sector?	Safety and job satisfaction are based on human factors, and human-machine behaviour research.

	proposing solutions to mitigate risks?			
Job Satisfaction	What tools and resources are available for employees to improve themselves in their positions?	How do you measure the overall satisfaction of your employees at the organisational level? How has technology and process development enabled the promotion of job satisfaction?	What measures have been taken to increase overall job satisfaction across the industrial sector?	Integration of digital systems, digital tools, machines and robots in organizational structural systems are enhancing the safety and job satisfaction.

Table 3. Key questions of benchmarking exercises on CAPS factors

SEISMEC Innovation areas

SEISMEC aims to bring the advanced technologies beyond the state-of-the-art by incorporating human-centric aspects into their application. Together with the CAPS, SEISMEC is conducting research to various innovation directions to enhance their compatibility and applicability of human-centric technology in real scenarios. The SEISMEC project aims to on four innovation directions as follows:

- Human-centrism assessment methods
- Interpretable Explainable AI (XAI) tools
- Advanced Methods for worker feedback
- Human-centric Interfaces for Decision Support and Digital Twins

Within the various innovation areas above, SEISMEC aims to achieve the Technology Readiness Level (TRL) and System Readiness Level (SRL) in enhancing the compatibility and applicability of human-centric technologies in real scenarios. The project will develop further the tools and methodologies of similar studies in the other projects as the basis of conceptual work. From the reference studies, SEISMEC aims to achieve the target of TRL/SRL on different innovation areas as follows:

Innovation and Reference Studies	Current TRL/SRL	Target TRL/SRL
<p>Human-centrism assessment methods</p> <p>Human-centrism assessment methods have been developed in the research context in the scope of the SPATIAL and ASHVIN H2020 projects and will be brought to operational environments in SEISMEC. In BRIDGES 5.0 projects, workforce skills will be brought to the Industry 5.0 level. The lessons of this project will be integrated into SEISMEC.</p>	4	7
<p>Interpretable Explainable AI tools</p> <p>CERTH will build on the I4Q and AIDEAS projects in the field of smart manufacturing and machinery industry, including XAI solutions that make the internal logic of the AI models transparent. Those solutions will be advanced and tailored to the SEISMEC AI models.</p>	4	6

<p>Advanced Methods for worker feedback</p> <p>Tools developed in the research context of the Dem@Care and Suiteyes projects, encompassing sentiment analysis, object and activity recognition, and smart wearable monitoring, will be adapted and exploited for the operation environments in SEISMEC.</p>	3	6
<p>Human-centric interfaces for Decision Support and Digital Twin</p> <p>The tools and techniques developed in the research context of the SUN project, which focuses on creating virtual environments and object digital twins, will be utilised to improve Human-Centric Interfaces for Decision Support and Digital Twins within the SEISMEC project. In addition, the DDT (Damage Detection Tool), GISI (GIS Integrator), and RISA (Risk-Based Asset Management Tool), developed through the joint efforts of CERTH and INFRAPLAN for the Zadar Airport demo case in ASHVIN will be extended to become more human-centric.</p>	4	6

Table 4. Pilots intended and current TRL from reference studies

The four innovation areas above are deployed in the following tasks: T2.3 Method Approach for Worker Participation in Technology Design and Application, T2.4 Explainable AI methods for human-technology trustworthiness, T2.5 Privacy-preserving models and methods for worker feedback and T2.6 Tools for redesigning Human-Centric Interfaces.

2.1.4 KPIs Criteria for Evaluation

Key performance indicators (KPIs) are defined as the metrics or indicators used to evaluate the performance of an organisation in achieving its strategic objectives (Parmenter, 2015). By tracking KPIs, an organisation is able to assess the progress, identify areas for improvements and make informed decision to drive growth and success. KPIs highlight key areas that require attention and monitoring, hence serve as guiding compass towards the desired outcomes. According to Parmenter (2015), the characteristics of KPIs shall be lingered in non-financial aspects that give significant impacts with limited potential negative consequences to the organisations. Therefore, it is crucial to ensure that the KPIs encourage the desired behaviours beneficial to the organization. It is also

important to acknowledge that the diverse nature of pilots generates the KPIs that require broader and generalised approaches, rather than represent each pilot individually.

Alongside the CAPS factors and the four innovation areas, SEISMEC will develop specific KPIs based on literature and the prior work of research partners. These KPIs will be used to evaluate the outlined research directions. Combined they form the MS5 “KPIs – Initial Criteria for Evaluation” list, as part of the work conducted in T2.2 Development of Instruments and Assessment Criteria. The MS5 list is a living list which will be continuously updated until the end of the task in M18. The KPIs of CAPS factors may be derived from Likert scale exercise of benchmarking human-centrism assessment of Deliverable 1.1. The KPIs are described respectively based on the assessment categories in Collaboration, Creativity, Automation, Autonomy, Privacy, Productivity, Safety and job Satisfaction. The potential KPIs of CAPS factors are shown on **Table 7**.

On the other hand, the KPIs of four innovation areas are derived from the tasks T2.3 Method Approach for Worker Participation in Technology Design and Application, T2.4 Explainable AI methods for human-technology trustworthiness, T2.5 Privacy preserving models and methods for worker feedback and T2.6 Tools for redesigning Human-Centric Interfaces. They are identified for evaluating the SEISMEC tools by using **Specific Metrics for Evaluation** as follows:

— **Human-Centrism Assessment Methods:**

User Satisfaction: Measured via surveys

Adoption Rate: Percentage of workforce adopting the methods

Assessment Accuracy: The accuracy of assessment tools

— **Interpretable Explainable AI Tools:**

Model Transparency: Percentage of AI models with interpretable results

User Understanding: Survey-based score on user understanding of AI decisions

Integration Success: Successful integration rate into SEISMEC models

Evaluation of Interpretable Explainable AI Tools are measured with 1) Human-Grounded metrics, 2) Application-Grounded metrics and 3)

Functionally Grounded metrics, including metrics like Stability, Faithfulness, Complexity/ Comprehensibility, Fidelity etc. More analytical explanation of the initial metrics is further explained in the document MS5 “KPIs – Initial Criteria for Evaluation”.

— **Advanced Methods for Worker Feedback:**

As part of Task 2.5, the methods deployed will be assessed through various KPIs, focusing on aspects such as predictive and computer vision performance, inference time, and user satisfaction as measured from processing information from passive and active sensors. Table 6 indicates several initial KPIs and the associated technology that may be implemented, depending on the needs of use case.

KPI id	KPI Description	Associated Technology
1	Prediction AI models' performance in accuracy or R ² score	Sentiment analysis, Eye gaze
2	Object Keypoint Similarity	Pose estimation
3	Mean Average Precision (IoU50)	Object detection
4	Operate with multiple targets	Pose estimation
5	Inference time of AI tools	All technologies
6	User satisfaction (Likert scale)	All technologies

Table 5. KPIs on Worker Feedback

— **Human-Centric Interfaces for Decision Support and Digital Twins:**

- Interface Usability: Usability score from user testing
- Decision Accuracy: Improvement in decision-making accuracy
- System Integration: Rate of successful integration with existing systems

All of the above metrics will influence the evaluation phase which is described Chapter 3.3.

Benchmarking exercise		KPIs of CAPS
Collaboration	The degree of collaboration between humans and digital systems (robots, machines, digital tools) within your organization.	Increasing collaborative work amongst human-digital system within organisation
Creativity	Organizational results, performance, efficiency and productivity are influenced by the relation between human - centrism / affect and creativity.	Increasing efficiency & productivity as a result of human - digital system relationship
Autonomy	The degree of human autonomy based on human - machine interaction?	Progressive human autonomy as a result of human - machine interaction
Automation	Human safety, trust, workload and behaviour are taken into consideration in automating tasks and activities within your organization.	High degree of automated systems within organisation which consider human behaviour, safety, trust and workload.
Privacy	Occupational risks are taken into consideration in human-centric computing, human-machine interaction and collaboration and integration of AI in human work processes.	Low occupational risks on human-centric computing and human-machine integration
Productivity	Data-driven approaches are implemented to enhance productivity and privacy.	High level of application in data-driven methods in enhancing privacy and productivity
Safety	Safety and job satisfaction are based on human factors, and human-machine behaviour research.	Increasing priority on safety and job satisfaction during human-centric and human-machine behaviour research
Job Satisfaction	Integration of digital systems, digital tools, machines and robots in organizational structural systems are enhancing the safety and job satisfaction.	Increasing number of integrated digital tools and machines in enhancing safety and job satisfaction.

Table 6. KPIs on CAPS factors based on benchmarking exercise

2.1.5 Challenges in Human-centric Research

Understanding the challenges in human-centric research is a crucial step as it ensures the methodology aligns with the dynamic and diverse needs of end-users and stakeholders. As a consequence, addressing the challenges will enhance effectiveness and relevance of the project (Norman, 2013; Sanders & Stappers, 2008). This section addresses challenges which may impact the data collection protocols of WP1 and WP2 and the application framework for WP4 and WP5, thus exploring the complexities and overcoming strategies are crucial.

Challenges in human-centric research persist in distinguishing between two aims: using research data to understand human-centrism as a phenomenon or acquiring data necessary for AI and other ubiquitous computing tools for systemic co-design development. One primary challenge in human-centric research is understanding the diverse and dynamic needs, behaviours, and experiences of individuals within various contexts (Norman, 2013). As human development evolves, so do the challenges associated with human-centrism. Effective collaboration between researchers, designers, engineers, and end-users prior to implementation is crucial to ensure that the solutions are practical, accepted, and beneficial to users (Sanders & Stappers, 2008). This collaborative effort is essential for developing tools and systems that genuinely reflect and address human needs, ultimately enhancing user satisfaction and system effectiveness (Bannon, 2011).

Another significant challenge is integrating qualitative and quantitative data to create a holistic understanding of user needs and experiences. Data collected through surveys, observations, interviews, and focus group discussions (FGDs) provide valuable insights but require careful analysis and interpretation to be applicable as they are fully dominated by subjective perspectives. Surveys and quantitative data (charts, graphs, statistics) need to be complemented with qualitative data (photographs, voice recordings, transcripts) to form a comprehensive picture (Creswell & Plano Clark, 2017). This integration can be resource-intensive and requires advanced analytical tools and methodologies.

A further challenge is managing and securing the extensive data collected, particularly with concerns regarding privacy and ethical considerations. The principle of data management is crucial for ensuring the ethical handling of data, which involves anonymizing sensitive information and obtaining informed consent from participants (Smith, Milberg, & Burke, 1996). Balancing the need for detailed data collection with the ethical obligation to protect participant privacy is a continual challenge.

Overcoming the challenges in human-centric research requires a multifaceted approach that integrates collaborative design, advanced data integration techniques, ethical data management, and iterative feedback and evaluation. Collaborative design and development involve active participation in the design process, ensuring their needs and feedback are integrated, leading to more adaptable and effective solutions (Simonsen & Robertson, 2012). Advanced data integration techniques by combining mixed-methods of qualitative and quantitative data will provide a richer understanding of user needs (Creswell & Plano Clark, 2017), making the data more applicable. Finally, an iterative feedback and regular evaluation process involving continuous feedback loops and updates from the users is crucial to ensure the system developed remain effective and productive (Schön, 1983).

2.2 Piloting Process Methodology

Piloting in SEISMEC is an iterative and continued process. Collaboratively with all research partners and pilots, the details of piloting process will be periodically updated through a number of activities, including workshops, observations, surveys and interviews. The update of piloting details will be documented in forms of meeting minutes; comprehensive observation notes; graphs, charts and tables from workshops encryptions; and interview transcriptions which will be compiled systematically in digital databases for easy accessibility.

The documentation will be arranged in a chronological sequence and be recorded in detailed logbook to record information obtained from each activity. A regular review and update to the documentation will be scheduled in a periodic review

meeting or workshop, ideally every quarter or every six months each year. The piloting review and process will involve all pilots' stakeholders to ensure the documentation remains current and comprehensive. The piloting process will utilise research instruments defined **WP2 Tools and Methods towards Human-centrism**. The research methods and tools may be divided into quadrant of behavioural and attitudinal in qualitative and quantitative methodology based on the characteristic of data collection tools shown in **Figure 4** (Rohrer, 2022).

The graph illustrates the quadrant of various data collection methodologies categorised by the nature of the how metadata is collected. According to Rohrer (2022), attitudinal and behavioural methods are generated based on the participants' responses during the research. The attitudinal research aims to understand or measure the nature of the participants, but it is limited by what they are aware of and willing to report, in other word, it is self-reported. On the other side, the behavioural research seek to understand the participants' natural interactions with the products or services in questions, with little to no filtering from the participants themselves.

In the qualitative studies, the data are gathered by conducting observations, interviews or discussions directly to the participants, generating descriptive data in the form of visual, audio, and written. Meanwhile, in the quantitative studies, the researchers gather data indirectly to participants using measurements or instruments which generates quantifiable data in the form of numbers, tables or charts. The suitable methods and tools for researching pilots will be further define in the T2.2 Development of Instruments and Assessment Criteria.

Figure 4. Quadrant of potential methods and tools (Rohrer, 2022)

This section presents a diverse set of data necessary for piloting process. The content of the chapter includes:

- Assessment on piloting planning activities conducted
- Variety of focus area of improvement
- Category of task innovation within different sectors of pilots
- Technology overview based on pilot contexts
- The pilot objectives on CAPS empowerment factors and TRL.

2.2.1 Piloting Planning Activities Conducted

Piloting planning activities describe the activities conducted and document the pilot activities. The piloting planning activity was started by conducting **four initial workshops** to gather detailed data on the partners, which will be periodically

updated. The workshops aim to obtain necessary data that would be beneficial for implementing advanced technology. The data will include:

- Ideation and vision of pilots’ advanced technology;
- Desired timeline for technology implementation;
- Pilots’ company structure;
- Envision of advanced technologies’ users;
- Pilots’ chosen CAPS factors; and
- Plan of data collection.

Table 8 shows the participants and agenda of initial piloting workshops. The general results of the workshops are summarised in the Table 9. Further pilots are planned for later dates.

Activity	Date	Participants	Agenda
Pilot Workshop #1	24.04.2024	Kvaletitas MOW THALES FARM.NOW ARCTUR	Discussing: Ideation for technology, implementation timeline, envision of users, company structures, CAPS factors,
Pilot Workshop #2	30.04.2024	MOW NSWD ATES	Data collection plan
Pilot Workshop #3	02.05.2024	ZAG SELANA	
Pilot Workshop #4	12.06.2024	PIAC	

Table 7. Initial Pilot Workshop in M4-M6

Name of Partners	Advanced Technology	Assessment method	Number of Participants	Company Structures	How to reach users	Comments
ZAG	AI, CC, HMI, IoT	compliance with regulations, interview with workers	10	Large Company: IT teams, director of Informatics, Fire brigade, Inspection workers, air side safety, inspection team	meeting with workers, contact with ZAG	Started collecting information from employees
Kvalitetas	AI, IoT, WES, TOS	AI solution; skill survey; technology assessment; manufacturing survey;	7	Large Company: 3 management, 4 manufacturing	internal, online interviews, survey	
MC, MCH						New partner
MOW	AI, IoT, WES, TOS	Detect risky situation using machine learning, identify preliminary assumption	2-3	Large Company	Workers feedback in construction site	Weight measurement, post detection to anticipate human behaviour
NSWD	AI, SN	skill assessment, eye tracking	15 - 20 users	SME: 1 CEO, 2 founders	contact NS Web team	interested in job satisfaction, worker security
NTTD	AI, SN					To be determined
IFAT	AI, HMI					To be determined
ATLAS Copco	AI, DA					To be determined

<p>ATES</p>	<p>VR, SIM</p>	<p>VR for training & personal test</p>	<p>20: 10 experienced, 10 inexperienced</p>	<p>Large Company: HR, Production, Quality Control, Occupational Health and Safety, Maintenance, Purchasing, Finance, Planning, Project Management, Business Development, Information Technology, Research and Development.</p> <p>3 factories and a Worker Council of 7 representatives: 4 for Tower Factory, 2 for Generator Factory, and 1 for Machining Factory.</p>	<p>Potential users of VR technologies: Inexperienced and experienced employees of VR trainings in “Welding” and “Working at Height”.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - System will involve VR technologies. No sensors will be a part of system. - VR system will be applied in a special designed environment at ATES facility. - Results of training and tests using VR, feedback of observer (employees’ behaviors during VR training and test), pre-surveys and post-surveys.
<p>DIJ</p>	<p>AI, BD, CC, MD</p>					<p>New partner</p>
<p>MICHELIN</p>	<p>AI, CC, MD</p>					<p>To be determined</p>
<p>THALES</p>	<p>TOS, VR</p>	<p>VR headset with AI on drone to detect motion, AR for immersive interface on pilot</p>	<p>10</p>	<p>Large Company</p>	<p>Trust and skill assessments without clients</p>	<p>Data collecting has been started</p>

SELANA	AI, CC, MD	AI automation to ease route planning for changing batteries	1	Start-Up: 8 people	Via Selana, personalised system for Start-up, warehouse	Avoid FGD or other large-scale data collecting due to low number of participants.
Farm Now	AI, AT, HMD, WD	AI for material and predictive analysis; AR/VR/MR to see instant farming grows;	3-15	Start-Up: With up to 50-60 people consists of Executive team, Farm management, Farm hands	FGD, post-interviews	Require scientific impact KPI with action research cycle for multi-sensory system in different location.
PIAC	AI, AR	Collaboration between human and AI assessment	2-4	Large Company: — Production, — Quality control	Inspections to the operators	Expect to have one on one collaboration with the chosen partner after General Assembly
ARCTUR	AI, BD, MD	AI for collecting data and estimation of potential users	To be determined	SME with different groups: - Green Karst; - local tourist organisations	Through Green Karst Joint workshop with service providers	Expand to open source in region to get broader information. Envision to start in M6 with further details are under consideration
Malt	AI, BD, CC, MD					To be determined

Table 8. Pilot Workshop Encryption

2.2.2 Pilots' Focus Area of Improvement

With a diverse set of industrial sectors, pilots show a variety of focus areas of improvement to apply the advanced technologies of their choices. SEISMEC classifies the focus areas into several categories:

— Anomaly detection

Anomaly detection uses AI to identify patterns or behaviours that deviate from the norm within a dataset in order to detect issues before they become significant problems.

— Decision support and forecasting

Decision support and forecasting leverage AI and BD to assist human decision-makers by providing relevant information, predictive analytics, and recommendations to enhance strategic planning and problem-solving capabilities.

— Function support

Function support uses AI technology to assist operators and users in repetitive and manual tasks in order to improve work efficiency and ensure safer work environment.

— Working Environment Improvement

Working environment improvement aims to foster creativity, collaboration and increase job satisfaction of the employees in human resources, especially with the challenges of post-pandemic lack of interaction and communication. AI, SN, BD, and MD are utilised in developing personalised journey of the employees.

— Training and Interfaces

Training and interfaces may use VR, AR, and HMI to provide immersive and interactive training experiences. These technologies help workers to quickly acquire new skills, understand complex systems, and safely practice tasks in a simulated environment before applying them in the real world.

— Instruct Service Personnel

Instruct service personnel may use AI, CC, DA, and MD to increase autonomy in maintenance and technical support, thus improving productivity and skills of employees.

— Remote Control Interface

Remote Control Interfaces utilize IoT, CC, TOS to allow operators to manage and control machinery and processes from a distance. It is essential in hazardous environment or remote locations where the technology ensures continuity of operations while keeping human operators safe.

— Scheduling and Route Planning

Scheduling and route planning may utilise AI, CC and MD to develop automated system for creating most efficient routes and schedule, aiming to optimise and increase job satisfaction in mobility sector.

SEISMEC pilots present variety of advanced technology aimed to be implemented along with their focus area of improvements as shown in **Table 10**.

2.2.3 Pilots' Tasks of Innovation

SEISMEC aims at piloting human-centric improvements in advanced digital technology for work organisations and employees. The human-centric approaches are organised in four innovation areas:

— Work organisation (T3.1)

Work organisation comprises examining the tasks and functions of work organisations or companies.

— Skills and training (T3.2)

Skills and training comprise an application in innovations in skills and training, as well as health and safety.

— Enterprise management and governance (T3.3)

Enterprise management and governance comprises management and governance, business models, and corporate values and ethics.

— Tasks and functions of workers (T3.4)

Tasks and functions of workers comprises organising and monitoring the tasks and functions of workers.

Each pilot presents different tasks of innovations (See **Table 11**) which requires to apply attentive feedback loops between workers and work organisations to develop contextual advanced technology of their needs.

Name of Partners	Chosen Advanced Technology	Focus area of Improvements
ZAG	AI, CC, HMI, IoT	Anomaly detection
Kvalitetas	AI, IoT, WES, TOS	Decision support
MC,MCH	AI	Function support
MOW	AI, IoT, WES, TOS	Decision support
NSWD	AI, SN	Working environment Improvement
NTTD	AI, SN	Working environment Improvement
IFAT	AI, HMI	Training and interfaces
ATLAS Copco	AI, DA	Instruct service personnel
ATES	VR, SIM	Training and interfaces
DIJ	AI	Decision support
MICHELIN	AI, CC, MD	Instruct service personnel
THALES	TOS, VR	Remote control interface
BonSELANAdi	AI, CC, MD	Scheduling and route planning
FarmNow	AI, AT, HMD, WD	Training and monitoring
PIAC	AI, AR	Anomaly detection
ARCTUR	AI, BD, MD	Decision support
Malt	AI, BD, CC, MD	Working environment Improvement

Table 9. Pilot advanced technology and area of improvements

Name of Partners	Work Organisation (T3.1)	Skills & Training (T3.2)	Health and Safety (T3.2)	Management & governance (T3.3)	Business model (T3.3)	Corporate values and ethics (T3.3)	Tasks and functions (T3.4)
ZAG			X				X
Kvalitetas					X		X
MC, MCH			X				X
MOW	X					X	
NSWD	X	X					
NTTD	X			X		X	
IFAT		X					X
ATLAS Copco	X	X					
ATES		X	X				
DIJ	X			X			
MICHELIN	X	X					
THALES		X	X				X
SELANA	X						
FarmNow		X	X				
PIAC				X			X
ARCTUR	X	X		X	X		
Malt	X			X	X	X	

Table 10. Pilots’ Tasks of Innovation

2.2.4 Pilots' CAPS factors

The SEISMEC project uses CAPS factors as framework tensions to consider the relevant dimensions in research objectives and advanced technology implementation. To apply CAPS factors, pilots shall first identify the goals of the companies and the relevant advanced technologies they aim to implement. The inclusion of CAPS factors in pilots is crucial to ensure that pilots not only focus on technological advancement but also enhance essential aspects of the mutual relationships between human and digital systems in workplaces. By identifying CAPS factors based on pilots' necessities and their goals, SEISMEC will maximize the effectiveness and impact of human-centric technological innovations on the evolving needs and goals of the companies.

Pilots in SEISMEC may have one or more CAPS factors, which are linked to the necessities of task implementation along with the advanced technologies of their choice. The pilots will display different CAPS factors, influenced by the goals of technology improvement of the company (See **Table 12**). The CAPS factors of the pilots are gathered based on information obtained in meetings, workshops, surveys, interviews and focus group discussions. Blank spaces shall be filled after data collection activities with pilots are conducted. Any updates will be documented annually and continuously incorporated in Monitoring Documents D7.3 and D7.4.

Name of Partners	CAPS factor (Based on Workshop)
ZAG	Autonomy & Automation, Safety
Kvalitetas	To be determined
MC, MCH	(new partner)
MOW	Autonomy & Automation
NSWD	Privacy & Productivity, Safety & job satisfaction
NTTD	Collaboration & Creativity, Autonomy & Automation, Safety
IFAT	Safety & job satisfaction
ATLAS Copco	To be determined
ATES	To be determined
DIJ	(new partner)
MICHELIN	Autonomy & Automation, Privacy & Productivity
THALES	To be determined
SELANA	To be determined
FarmNow	Autonomy & Automation, job Satisfaction
PIAC	Collaboration, Autonomy, Productivity, job satisfaction
ARCTUR	To be determined
Malt	Collaboration & Creativity, Autonomy & Automation

Table 11. Pilot CAPS factor

3 Case Study Research and Method

SEISMEC focuses on the implementation of human-centric approaches through users engagement demonstrated in a diverse set of pilots. Understanding the users, in this case employees, are beneficial to improve companies' achievements (Budriene and Diskiene, 2020). Numerous studies around the world show that employee engagement has positive correlation to a company's performance in achieving high productivity and profitability (Demerouti and Cropanzano, 2010; Guest, 2014; Soni 2013), because engaged employees are willing to put effort into reaching optimal performance hence led to company's success (Budriene and Diskiene, 2020). According to Budriene and Diskiene (2020), engagement has three important elements, which are:

- **Cognitive: faith in the shared values and goals;**
- **Emotional: feeling of satisfaction and belonging;**
- **Behaviours: effort on willingness to take steps further.**

The SEISMEC project, with a focus on human-centrism in industries, aims to empower skilled employees by enhancing their professional competitiveness as well as promoting their involvement in a participatory and democratised manner within the work organisation. The three elements above are vital in understanding different perspectives of the two types of user engagements: employees and work organisation (Saks, 2006 in Budriene and Diskiene, 2020), which is essential for succeeding human-centrism in industries. Within a diverse set of industrial sectors, the research methodologies are influenced by the various research objectives on CAPS factors and innovation areas presented by different pilots. The SEISMEC project will develop research methodologies and tools by utilising **two-ways engagement of employees and work organizations** to contextualise the research objective based on subjective focus.

According to Guest (2014), the employee engagement will generate valuable information related to personal development and influencing factors such as work and team performance, intra-personal relationships with the co-workers, as well as potential opportunities and positive motivations for personal growth. On

the other hand, organisational engagement will generate data regarding companies' visions and values, strategic planning for employee growth and benefits, managerial leadership and professional relationships among different levels and stakeholders (Guest, 2014).

The two-way engagement research process will be divided into three phases: **Preparation Phase, Action Research Phase, and Evaluation Phase**. These phases are causally related and shall be iteratively conducted throughout the project (see **Figure 5**) tailored to the pilots' industries and their respective advanced technology. Each research phase will consider perspectives from both employees and companies, according to data collection and development in WP1, WP2, WP4, and WP5, which will be continuously monitored and organised in WP3. By integrating insights from the work packages, WP3 aims to determine contextual data collection methods within the three research phases to align with the tasks of T3.1, T3.2, T3.3, and T3.4 to achieve companies' goals in human-centrism. It is also important to emphasise that the transversal research requires a solid conceptual model prior to data collection, hence the selection of methods and tools is crucial.

In order to achieve the human-centrism aspects of the research, we highlight the ethnography approach for developing methods and tools of research in data collection process. The methods and tools of each phase will be documented throughout the piloting activity as seen on the example in **Table 13**. Each research phase and methodology will generate different datasets which are further explained in D7.2 Data, gender and quality management plan.

Figure 5. Three phases on case study research proces

Pilots	Tasks in WP3	Preparation Phase			Action Research Phase		Evaluation Phase		
		Pre – Survey	Ethno. Interview	Ethno. Observ.	Dev. Support	Implement. Phase	Post – Survey	Ethno. Interview	Ethno. Observ.
ZAG	3.2 , 3.4								
Kvalitetas	3.3 , 3.4								
MC, MCH	3.2 , 3.4								
MOW	3.1, 3.3								
NSWD	3.1, 3.3								
NTTD	3.1, 3.3								
IFAT	3.2 , 3.4								
ATLAS Copco	3.1, 3.2								
ATES	3.2								
DIJ	3.1, 3.3								
MICHELIN	3.1, 3.2								
THALES	3.2 , 3.4								
SELANA	3.1								
Farm Now	3.2 , 3.4								
PIAC	3.1,3.4								
AROTUR	3.1, 3.2, 3.3								
Malt	3.1, 3.3								

Table 12. Template of Pilot Research Plan based on Innovation Tasks

3.1 Preparation Phase

Preparation phase focuses on defining important elements prior conducting the research which include setting up potential participants, constructing suitable methodology, tools, as well as materials to assess concerns from the users. Preparation Phase will utilise research instruments defined in **WP2 Tools and Methods towards Human-centrism** with focus divisions on employees and companies. The preparation phase will explore concerns between employees and companies by utilising two-way engagement methods tools through ethnographic and other approaches with focus and perspective as illustrated in **Figure 6**.

The goals of the preparation phase are to obtain diverse spectrums of users' behaviours and attitudes in working environment as well as the compilation of work organisations' visions to develop potential ideation for implementation. Additionally, it provides benchmarking material to compare data over time, ensuring that subsequent steps in the project are based on a solid foundation of initial insights thus enhance productivity and efficiency.

Therefore, it is important to get the perspective of the users by conducting pre-surveys and interviews. The pre-survey aims to gather initial data and insights from both users. Pre-surveys for employees will include aspects such as job satisfaction (T4.3), worker autonomy (T4.3), skills assessment (T5.2), and the CAPS survey (T1.2). For companies, the pre-survey will focus on field analysis (T1.3), worker autonomy (T4.3), econometric assessment (T5.1), and the EU Manufacturing survey (T1.2). Interviews will then be conducted to delve deeper into specific areas. For employees, the interviews will cover field analysis (T1.3), cyber-security threats (T4.1), CAPS tension (T1.2), technology assessment (T2.4, T2.5, T2.6), and compliance with regulations (T5.4). For companies, the interviews will similarly focus on field analysis (T1.3), worker autonomy (T4.3), and other relevant areas.

To understand the profile of the participants, an ethnography approach of empathy map on user personas as illustrated in **Figure 7** (Gray,2017) may also be utilised in

preparation phase. Given that the research is focused on human-centricity, understanding the contextual behavior of humans is necessary, thus empathy maps will help in visualizing the users' experiences, needs, and challenges, thus ensuring a deeper understanding of both employees' and companies' perspectives.

By integrating both pre-survey data and interview insights, along with empathy mapping, the preparation phase aims to comprehensively understand and address the concerns of both employees and companies. This approach ensures that the research is grounded in the real-world experiences and needs of its participants, aligning with the overarching goal of human-centricity.

Figure 6. Preparation phase elements

Figure 7. Empathy map on user persona (Gray, 2017 with adjustment)

3.2 Action Research

The action research phase is a critical component of the research methodology in WP3, focusing on the iterative development and implementation of technical support systems based on data analysed during the preparation phase. The goals of the action research phase are to iteratively conduct technical support monitoring and test the proposed advanced technologies in diverse sets of industries of pilots. As depicted in **Figure 8**, this phase is structured into two primary segments: Technical Development Support and Implementation Phase.

The Technical Development Support segment aims to define and refine specific tasks essential for the project. These tasks include developing T2.4: explainable AI methods for human-technology trustworthiness, synergy and acceptance, T2.5: Privacy preserving models and methods for worker feedback, and T2.6: Tools for redesigning Human-Centric Interfaces. These tasks are pivotal in determining the most suitable application of AI and other advanced technologies for the pilot projects to be carried out in the implementation phase. The Implementation Phase

focuses on the practical application and iterative testing of the proposed technologies in diverse industry settings with pilot partners. This involves continuous user engagement through interviews and active participation to monitor and ensure the compatibility and efficacy of the advanced technology implementations. The iterative nature of this phase allows for ongoing adjustments and improvements based on real-world feedback and observations. Throughout the action research phase, both quantitative and qualitative methods will be employed to analyse the data and materials collected during the preparation phase. Various methodologies will be used as necessary, one of which is the technical development using technology radar (Smith, 2018) to evaluate and propose advanced technologies based on CAPS factors. These methods will be integral to the continued development and refinement of the project within WP2. In summary, the action research phase aims to serve as a dynamic and iterative process in bridging the gap between human-centrism and technological advancement by focusing on both technical support and real-world application.

Figure 8. Action research phase elements

Figure 9. Technology radar following CAPS factors (Smith, 2018 with adjustment)

3.3 Evaluation Phase

The evaluation phase aims to assess the outcomes of the research process and the compatibility of the chosen advanced technologies. This phase involves post-research analysis and investigation, iterating the data collection from the previous phases, and examining the technologies implemented to develop evidence-based, human-centric solutions through interviews. Focus group discussions will be conducted to incorporate two-way perspectives of employees and work organisation for an inclusive and contextual approach. Input for these discussions will be comparisons of results between the pilots. **Figure 10** illustrates the data collection process of evaluation phase.

Data analysis in the evaluation phase will involve iterative reviews to cross-analyse the compatibility of pilots and their innovation areas within WP4 Transversal Pilot Analysis. This process aims to produce evidence-based technologies that achieve optimal productivity in human-centric industries, as envisioned in WP5 Human-centrism for Strengthening Industrial Competitiveness. The reviews will integrate the results from WP1, WP2, WP4, and WP5.

The goal of the evaluation phase is to examine the compatibility of the proposed human-centric technologies with the profiles and visions of the pilot partners, thus answering the two main questions of the research. To achieve that, this phase develops and monitors different tasks as follows:

- **Impact of human-centric approaches measured by CAPS factors in achieving inclusive and productive advanced technologies within different innovation area:**
The evaluation phase will analyse how human-centric approaches, as measured by CAPS factors, impact the inclusiveness, productivity, and competitiveness of pilot projects. By using post-surveys interviews, and focus group discussions, the evaluation will gather data on privacy impact (T4.1), trust (T4.2), EU job satisfaction (T4.3), skills assessment (T5.2), worker autonomy (T4.3), and CAPS tensions (T1.2) of two different users. This comprehensive analysis will reveal how human-centric approaches facilitate influence the development of empowered and human-centered advanced technologies within different innovation areas.
- **Strategies and Methodologies in Monitoring and Coordinating Piloting Process:**
The evaluation phase will employ various strategies and methodologies to monitor and coordinate the piloting process. Through econometric assessments (T5.1), EU manufacturing surveys (T1.2), and compliance checks with regulations (T5.4), the evaluation will ensure continuous progress and issue resolution. These methods will be complemented by iterative reviews and focus group discussions, enabling a thorough examination of trust (T4.2), participation (T4.3), and the integration of AI, ubiquitous computing, and UX (T2.4, T2.5, T2.6). These efforts will provide a structured approach to track advancements and address any challenges that arise during the piloting process.

The evaluation phase's thorough analysis and iterative review process will deliver valuable insights to offer actionable recommendations for future implementations of human-centric advanced technologies.

Figure 10. Evaluation phase elements

4 Protocols, Frameworks, and Challenges

4.1 Data collection protocols of WP1 & WP2

SEISMEC will gather pilots' data using various data collection methodologies. The data collection process will use several tools which result in different formats of materials as follows:

- **Surveys:** consists of quantitative data in the form of visual and written materials including but not limited to charts, graphs, diagrams, cross tabulation, statistics, infographic and other quantifiable data.
- **Observations:** consists of qualitative data in the form of visual, audio, audio-visual and written materials including but not limited to photographs, voice recordings, video recordings, transcription, memos, and meeting minutes.
- **Interviews:** consists of qualitative data in the form of audio, audio-visual and written materials including but not limited to voice recordings, video recordings, interviewees profiles, and transcription.
- **FGD:** consists of combination of qualitative and quantitative data of participatory methodology in the form of visual, audio, audio-visual, and written materials, including but not limited to graphs, diagrams, feedback forms, voice recordings, video recordings, participant profiles, transcription, memos, and meeting minutes.

The data collection process will follow extensive research phases of **Preparation Phase, Action Research Phase, and Evaluation Phase** explained in **Chapter 3 Case Study Research and Method**. The first data collection of all pilots shall be done at the Preparation Phase in the beginning of the project, starting shortly after M6 and covering WP1 and WP2. The second data collection shall be done at Evaluation Phase to assess the final result of WP1 and WP2, hence applicable in WP4 and WP5. Pilots are expected to document their visions and developments in a report within the

format of at least **three pages of A4**. All collected data shall be documented and stored following a principle of data management as explained in **Chapter 6**.

4.2 Application Framework for WP4 & WP5

The application framework for WP4 and WP5 will be guided by detailed data referencing to ensure alignment with project objectives. **WP4 Transversal Pilot analyses** conducts cross-pilot and innovation-arena analyses as well as monitor the pilots' issues and their opportunities for wider applicability. Analyses in WP4 will cover various sectors of cyber security and privacy, human trust and understanding, the impact of worker co-design, as well as in-work learning and skills development. WP4 utilises data obtained in T2.2 to create user-centric solutions that enhance productivity and two-ways engagement between employees and work organisations.

WP5 Human-centrism for Strengthening Industrial Competitiveness focuses on deploying and testing advanced technology solutions to understand the evidence-based impacts and verify their effectiveness of human-centric technology in real environments. Technical support will be provided to ensure the effective implementation and integration of these applications, with continuous user collaboration during both the action research and post-evaluation phases. SEISMEC aims to engage broad users to gather comprehensive feedback and validate the solutions' practicality and benefits. Application frameworks for WP4 and WP5 will be systematically planned and integrated with the data management plan to ensure efficient data handling and analysis.

5 Piloting Schedule

Piloting is an iterative process throughout the project. The iteration aims to accommodate any changes or new insights that arise, allowing for continuous improvement and adaptation to meet the project's goals and challenges effectively.

The piloting schedule (**Table 14**) shows the plan of implementation timeline which will be continuously updated as the project progresses following their needs.

Name of Partners	2024				2025				2026				Note from Workshop
	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	
ZAG													
Kvalitetas													
MC, MCH													New partner
MOW													Anytime, 6 months
NSWD													
DIJ													New partner
IFAT													
ATLAS Copco													
ATES													
Healthcare													
MICHELIN													
THALES													In planning
SELANA													
Farm Now													Project duration
PIAC													Anytime
ARCTUR													
Malt													

Table 13. Piloting Schedule based on recent updates

6 Ethics, Privacy and Data Management

The SEISMEC project collaborates with multiple partners from various countries, industries and institutions. Within such broad contexts and backgrounds, the piloting process will involve sensitive data of partners, thus managing ethics, privacy and data collection amongst partners is crucial. Data management and ethics procedures shall take in place prior to the start of data collection, storage and sharing as part of pilot activities. The following section provide summary of management system and sharing agreement which are described in details in Deliverable D7.1 Project Management Plan.

6.1 Data Management

To ensure effective data management for the SEISMEC project, discussions have taken place with Steering Committee members who are directly involved in the pilot activities. As a result of these discussions, the following key components will be developed:

- A Dataflow chart
- A data management plan (D7.2 due by 30th of June 2024)
- Ethics approval

6.2 Data Privacy Related/ Required Agreements

Agreements aim to ensure all data handling practices within the SEISMEC project adhere to legal and ethical standards, protecting both personal and proprietary data throughout the research process. To ensure compliance with data privacy regulations and protect the rights of all participants involved, several key agreements are required as follows:

- Informed Consent Form

Consist of legal basis to collect and process personal data. It shall be signed by individual research participants

— **Joint Controllership Agreement (JCA)**

Agreement necessary when sharing research data containing personal data within the EEA. It shall be signed by Steering Committee members.

— **Standard Contractual Clause (SCC)**

Agreement necessary when sharing research data containing personal data to partners located outside EEA. Shall be signed by partners outside EU such as Türkiye and Serbia with counterparts receiving data.

— **Non-Disclosure Agreement (NDA)**

Protection of proprietary data. It shall be signed by any partners on as-need basis

Empirical data for social sciences analysis in the SEISMEC project includes personal data collected through surveys, interviews, observations, focus groups, and similar methods. The types of data are divided into two based on the data collection methodology:

Collected by research partners: informed consent forms, JCA, SCC

Provided by industry partner: informed consent forms, provides anonymised or synthetic data

Importantly, General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) does not apply to this data. For developing and implementing technology, data is provided by industry partners to research partners supporting pilot implementation. Ideally, this data is anonymized or synthetic. When anonymization is not possible, it is necessary to consider strategies as follow:

Establish Non-Disclosure Agreement (NDA) between the industry and research partners,

Restrict data access to research partners involved in pilot development, with a regulated access management protocol.

6.3 Ethics compliance: three-level approach

SEISMEC project adopts a comprehensive three-level approach to ensure ethics compliance as follows:

- **“Umbrella application” for whole project**

An umbrella application will cover the entire project, managed by the coordinating partner at the EU level. This application will provide a general review with submission date to the EUR Ethics Board on June 1st, 2024.

- **Subsequent applications outlining specifics of each interventions**

Research partners at their respective institutions will submit detailed applications for each specific intervention. These applications will undergo thorough reviews focusing on the applied technology, data involved, security measures, and other pertinent details. Approval must be obtained before commencing any sub-activity, and a copy of each approval will be provided to the project coordinator for documentation.

- **Declaration of Honour**

Industry partners will submit a Declaration of Honour to acknowledge their commitment to ethical standards.

Additionally, all partners will receive an ethical acknowledgment form, outlining general ethical guidelines. These guidelines ensure that all individuals are informed about new digital technologies being implemented and have completed informed consent forms when necessary. When necessary, Data Impact Assessments will be conducted before implementing new technologies, and all relevant privacy legislation will be applied to the deployment of digital technology tools.

7 Conclusion

SEISMEC project demonstrates an empowered, human-centred, and ethical development of digital and industrial sectors across Europe. The continuous and iterative piloting process is crucial, necessitating regular updates and immediate attention to changes. Each pilot's focus on four specific innovation areas requires tailored strategies, highlighting the importance of closely monitoring progress and maintaining regular reporting. WP3 will conduct piloting process to monitor and coordinate the pilot partners throughout the project closely.

To achieve the goal of monitoring, regular reporting and timely updates are crucial to ensure continuous progress and promptly address any issues. Effective communication among all partners, including pilots, institutions, researchers, engineers, and designers, shall be maintained to align the project aims facilitate problem-solving. This structured approach ensures that the project can adapt to changes efficiently and achieve its goal of advancing human-centred and ethical innovations in the digital and industrial sectors across Europe. As the piloting process is an iterative process, further updates following the progress of the project is deemed necessary. The updates will be documented annually and continuously incorporated in Monitoring Documents D7.3 and D7.4.

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